

Proclus on the Two Causal Models for the One's Production of Being: Reconciling the Relation of the Henads and the Limit/Unlimited

Jonathan Greig

Austrian Academy of Sciences (Institute for Medieval Research)

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Abstract

In Proclus' metaphysics, the One produces Being through a mediated set of principles which are the direct causes of Being. While the henads (ένάδες) feature prominently as these principles, Proclus posits a second set of principles, the Limit and Unlimited, to explain the aspects of unity and plurality found in all beings. Initially there seems to be a tension in these two sets of principles: Proclus does not immediately clarify how they interact with each other or their relationship to each other. In *Elements of Theology* Prop. 159, he even seems to say that the Limit/Unlimited produce the henads—which contradicts the henads' nature as pure 'ones'. This article analyzes this issue by surveying three contemporary solutions that have been posed to address the tension, while also offering a new alternative: the Limit and Unlimited, as the first henads to emerge from the One, causally determine all subsequent henads according to their respective unique character (ιδιότης), while both sets are ultimately derived from the One according to their subsistence (ύπαρξις)—preserving the henads' natures as purely 'one' like the One-itself.

Keywords

Proclus, Neoplatonism, first principles, causality

1. Introduction

Among other things, Proclus is well-known for developing a theory of causality according to which the One produces Being through intermediate causes—a contrast to the earlier Neoplatonist, Plotinus, for whom the One is the direct cause of Being.¹ Most people familiar with Proclus may immediately associate these causes with what the late Neoplatonist terms the 'henads' (ένάδες)—entities which share the same nature as the One as 'beyond being' (έπέκεινα τής ούσίας), beyond definition and positive predication, and are only known through their effects.² Proclus, however, elucidates a *second* set of intermediate causes also responsible for the production of Being: the Limit and Unlimited, principles which Proclus borrows from Plato's *Philebus* 16c–d where they are said to be the constitutive principles of all being.

¹ At least in the form of the principle, Intellect: see e.g. Plotinus, *Enn.* V.3.5, 33–48.

² On this see *Elements of Theology* (heretofore abbreviated '*ET*') Propositions 115 and 123. Page numbering for the *ET* is from Dodds' ed. (1963).

Proclus is noticeably silent on spelling out the exact relation between these two sets of intermediate causes. Those hoping to find passages where the two are reconciled may be disappointed by the initially unhelpful *Elements of Theology's* Prop. 159, where Proclus claims that the 'orders of gods'—or the henads, in other words—are 'derived from the first principles, Limit and Unlimitedness' (ἐκ τῶν πρώτων ἐστὶν ἀρχῶν, πέρατος καὶ ἀπειρίας) (138,30–32).³ On the one hand this suggests that the henads are subordinated under the Limit and Unlimited. But if so, this also suggests that the henads in themselves are composed—in turn breaking their status as pure unities. Proclus certainly cannot mean this sense of composition or subordination at any rate. Although he indicates that there is *some* relation between the Limit/Unlimited and the henads, Proclus is unfortunately scant on the details of this relation by which a conflict or contradiction can be avoided.

A number of solutions have been posited in contemporary work on Proclus to address this problem: among others, Gerd van Riel, Cristina d'Ancona, and Edward Butler. All three have given plausible interpretations, and have also raised important questions which are worth considering both among themselves and in relation to the texts. Thus in this article, I wish to consider these three interpretations and to give an overview of the passages where Proclus provides some indication of the relation between the henads and the Limit and Unlimited. I propose a new position that has not yet been considered in the scholarship: namely that Proclus considers the Limit and Unlimited as the first henads to come forth from the One, while the two principles, in turn, are responsible for the composition of the *characters* (ιδιότητες) distinguishing all subsequent henads that come forth from the One. Put simply, the One is then responsible for the subsistence (ὑπαρξίς)⁴ of all henads, while the Limit and Unlimited are responsible for the individuating characters of the henads that make up the different kinds, or orders, of henads responsible for their specific effects in Being.

2. Some Background (i): The One's Causality and the Henads

In order to understand how the tension first arises between the henads and the Limit/Unlimited, we should first consider Proclus' framework for the One's causality, where the two kinds of principles are necessitated. From this vantage point we may assess the kind of tension that arises, as well as the three contemporary attempts that address this tension.

The first, central place where we find Proclus discussing the One and the need for intermediate principles is in *ET* Prop's. 5 and 6.⁵ In Prop. 5, where he establishes the priority of the One before all

³ Translations are my own unless otherwise noted.

⁴ In the context of these passages I generally translate ὑπαρξίς as 'subsistence' and ὑπόστασις as 'existence'. Although the term can have varying meanings throughout his corpus, Proclus tends to use ὑπαρξίς in a more restricted sense to indicate the 'essence' or specific existence of an entity. By contrast Proclus tends to use ὑπόστασις in a general, looser sense to indicate the existence *in some way* of a given entity: e.g. the contrast between *παρὑπόστασις* as indicating an accidental existence, and ὑπόστασις as something existing by itself. For further background and a survey on ὑπαρξίς/ὑπόστασις in Proclus, see C. Steel (1994).

⁵ For a thoroughly detailed analysis of these propositions (1–6) establishing the One, see J. Opsomer (2013) 627–32. I also discuss these propositions in a forthcoming monograph comparing Proclus and his successor, Damascius, on the One's causality and the first principle. See also G. Van Riel (2016), esp. 73–82, for an overview of Proclus' metaphysical structure.

plurality, Proclus narrows in on a specific type of priority: one which does not involve participation in plurality. In the last part of the proof, Proclus considers a hypothetical ‘One’ which is prior to plurality and directly acts on it by unifying it: the ‘One’ in this case would still be affected by that plurality through its ‘participation’ in plurality, since they ‘communicate in each other in some way’ while the ‘One’ unifies that plurality.⁶ Thus a distinct principle is needed to bring the ‘One’ and plurality together: for Proclus this would be the ‘One-itself’ (τὸ αὐτοέν), rather than a ‘One’.⁷

It is in the next Prop. 6 that Proclus universalizes this specific case for all pluralities: the first pluralities in being must come from entities that are purely ‘one’ by their nature—thus ‘henads’ (ἐνάδες)—implicitly after the ‘One-itself’.⁸ This is intimately connected with a general causal principle, employed later in *ET* Prop. 23, that the participants of a given effect receive that property from two types of causes: the unparticipated, as the general cause of that effect, and the participated, as the immediate cause of a specific participant receiving that property.⁹ In this regard Proclus marks a sharp departure from earlier Platonists like Plotinus, for whom there is no such distinction;¹⁰ instead for Proclus, as implicit above, causes that act directly on their effect are contextualized by that which they act on. Thus the particular variation of one participant compared to another correspondingly reflects the kind of cause that acts on that participant.

This becomes an issue when we look at the henads in themselves: in particular how it is possible that, as ‘one’ like the One-itself, they are indistinguishable while still numerically distinct. Proclus initially discusses this in *ET* Prop. 116, where he establishes that ‘every god¹¹ is participated, except the One’ (πᾶς θεὸς μεθεκτός ἐστι, πλὴν τοῦ ἑνός) (102,13). In the beginning of the proof, Proclus repeats the principle from Prop. 23 that, if the One-itself were participated, it would only be the principle of one particular effect and not the cause of both ‘the entities before being (τῶν προόντων) and of beings’.¹² More importantly for us, Proclus shows how the henads are distinct from the One in the second part of the proposition:¹³ if a given entity is not ‘not-one’ by its existence (ὑπόστασις),¹⁴ then it will be purely ‘one’, and thus the unparticipated One-itself; but if it is a certain existence (ὑπόστασις τις) other than pure

⁶ *ET* Prop. 5, 6,10–11: τὰ δὲ συνιόντα καὶ κοινωνοῦντά πη ἀλλήλοις εἰ μὲν ὑπ’ ἄλλου συνάγεται.

⁷ *ET* Prop. 5, 6,7–13.

⁸ *ET* Prop. 6, 6,22.

⁹ *ET* Prop. 23, esp. 26,30–34.

¹⁰ Among various passages in Plotinus, see *Enn.* VI.4.3, 12–19. On participation in general in Plotinus, see also S. Strange (1992) alongside R. Chiaradonna (2014).

¹¹ Implicitly ‘henads’: for Proclus the gods are characterized in their nature by unity, and therefore fit the definition of particular ‘ones’, or henads, from Prop. 6. See *ET* Prop. 113.

¹² *ET* Prop. 116, 102,14–16: μηκέτι πάντων ὁμοίως ἢ τῶν τε προόντων καὶ τῶν ὄντων αἴτιον.

¹³ *ET* Prop. 116, 102,17–27.

¹⁴ See previous n. 4.

unity, then it will be participated by what is not-one (ὑπὸ τοῦ οὐχ ἑνός)¹⁵—i.e. implicitly by beings—thus a henad. In *Platonic Theology*¹⁶ III.4, Proclus elaborates on this latter sense for the henads when he resolves the *aporia* of how the henads, as intermediaries, produce entities entirely dissimilar to the One-itself, yet share the One's nature.¹⁷ In the passage, Proclus maintains that 'through itself' (δι' ἑαυτοῦ) each henad 'reverts all things towards [the One]' (πρὸς ἐκεῖνο πάντα ἐπιστρέφει) (16,4–5)—similar to Proclus' discussion of each henad being 'self-complete' (αὐτοτελής) in *ET Prop.*'s. 114 and 131.¹⁸ Consequently each henad 'contains together' (συνέχει) its varying effects dissimilar to its own nature.¹⁹

From this we can see the henads being 'self-complete' links them to the One, while the respect in which each is 'self-complete'—particularly with the specific types of effects that each distinctly 'contains together' (συνέχει) and produces—is what demarcates one henad from another, and in turn from the One.²⁰ Thus we can tentatively observe Proclus' framework for the production of Being sketched out: the One anchors the unity of the henads, while the latter in turn are the first, direct causes of the different classes and orders of Being.²¹

3. Some Background (ii): The Limit and the Unlimited

Given Proclus' framework for the henads, one may wonder what need there is to posit any other causal model to explain the production of Being. And yet Proclus does indeed posit such an additional model in *ET Prop.*'s. 89 and 90. In Prop. 89 Proclus establishes that Being (πᾶν τὸ ὄντως ὄν) is composed from the elements of 'limit' (πέρας) and 'unlimited' (ἄπειρον). Because Being subsists as a 'mixed' (μικτόν) entity from the two characters, Proclus establishes the necessity for principles behind these two characters—the Limit-itself and the Unlimited-itself.²² As one can see from one passage in the *Parmenides Commentary*,²³ Proclus demonstrates how the Limit and Unlimited account for various manifestations of unity and plurality in all beings—from the point and extension in mathematics (for limit, unlimited respectively), to equality/inequality in quantity, likeness/unlikeness in qualities, implicitly up to form and matter: in all cases the 'limiting' factor brings about order and structure to 'those things that had until then been unlimited by virtue of their own nature' (τὰ τέως ἄπειρα κατὰ τὴν

¹⁵ 102,21–23: ἀλλὰ τὸ οὐχ ἑν τοῦτο εἰ μὲν μηδεμία ὑπόστασις, ἔσται μόνον ἑν· εἰ δὲ ὑπόστασις τις ἄλλη παρὰ τὸ ἑν, μετεχόμενον ἔσται τὸ ἑν ὑπὸ τοῦ οὐχ ἑνός.

¹⁶ Here onward abbreviated '*PT*'. Citations from Westerink-Saffrey ed.

¹⁷ *PT* III.4, esp. 15,27–16,7.

¹⁸ See esp. 116,23–25.

¹⁹ 16,2–4. For a discussion of 'containing causes' (συνεχτικόν) in Proclus, see C. Steel (2002).

²⁰ Proclus will refer to a henad's 'unique character' (ιδιότης) as its distinguisher in relation to its subsistence (ὑπαρξίς) as pure unity: see e.g. *ET Prop.* 162, 140,31–142,8.

²¹ How one is to understand the exact relation between the One and the henads becomes a disputed question as we will see in Edward Butler's position, discussed below.

²² *ET Prop.* 90.

²³ Here onward abbreviated '*In Parm.*'; citations from Steel ed.

αὐτῶν φύσιν).²⁴ Since all instances of being up to Being-itself display these two properties, for Proclus the two causes of Being must be two prior principles: Limit-itself and Unlimited-itself.

One may wonder here where the Limit and Unlimited stand. If they are before Being, as composing the elements within Being, then they would also fall in between the One and Being, just like the henads. Yet in his discussion from the previous passages, Proclus does not specify what relation the two principles have to the One or especially the henads. It is clear that they have a kind of mediating causality between the One and Being, inasmuch as they are responsible for the combination of unity and plurality in Being. Yet crucially how they relate to the henads—which are also mediating causes between the One and Being—is something that is not immediately apparent.

One passage that gives us an indication is *PT* III.9, where Proclus provides an exegesis of Plato's *Philebus* 23c where Socrates presents the Limit and Unlimited as 'revealed' (δείξει) by God. In his interpretation, Proclus takes δείξει to suggest that the two principles are 'henads constituted from the One and, as it were, manifestations from the unparticipated and very first unity'.²⁵ On the one hand, by using the same terminology, Proclus seems to identify the Limit/Unlimited straightforwardly with the 'henads' of *ET* Prop. 6. Yet this reading may not be so straightforward: the fact that Proclus focuses on just the Limit and Unlimited here would suggest that they are the first *two* henads before the other henads—or this might also suggest they are 'henads' in a very different sense from that of Prop. 6. Although Proclus does not elaborate this in the passage, it is clear that he thinks the Limit and Unlimited are two causal principles derived from the One, and Being's production is summed up in their 'manifestation'. Whether in the same way as the henads or in a distinct way remains to be seen.

4. Tension in Reconciling Two Models

The relation of the Limit and Unlimited to the henads comes to the fore when we look back at the *Elements'* propositions on the various classes of gods (such as 'paternal', 'generative', etc.)²⁶ and consider the enigmatic Prop. 159, as mentioned in the beginning, where Proclus claims that 'every order of gods is derived from the first principles, Limit and Unlimitedness' (πάσα τάξις θεῶν ἐκ τῶν πρώτων ἐστὶν ἀρχῶν, πέραςτος καὶ ἀπειρίας):

For everything proceeds from both, since the communications of the first causes extend through all secondary principles. But at some points the Limit dominates in the mixture, and at other points the Unlimited. And in this way one kind with the form of limit results, in which elements of the limit prevail; and another kind with the form of the unlimited results, in which elements of the unlimited prevail. (*ET* Prop. 159, 138,33–140,4)

πάσα μὲν γὰρ ἐξ ἀμφοτέρων πρόεισι, διότι τῶν πρώτων αἰτίων αἱ μεταδόσεις διήκουσι διὰ πάντων τῶν δευτέρων. Ἄλλ' ὅπου μὲν τὸ πέρας ἐνδυναστεύει κατὰ τὴν μίξιν, ὅπου δὲ τὸ ἀπειρον· καὶ οὕτω

²⁴ *In Parm.* 937,30–938,8. Cf. *PT* III.8, 30,19–26, and *In Crat.* 42,3–4; for a further discussion of the Limit/Unlimited, see R. Chlup (2012) 78 ff.

²⁵ *PT* III.9, 36,10–19, esp. here 13–15: ἑνάδες γὰρ εἰσὶν ἀπὸ τοῦ ἐνός ὑποστάσαι καὶ οἶον ἐκφάνσεις ἀπὸ τῆς ἀμεθέκτου καὶ πρωτίστης ἐνώσεως.

²⁶ *ET* Prop's. 151–158.

δὴ τὸ μὲν περατοειδὲς ἀποτελεῖται γένος, ἐν ᾧ τὰ τοῦ πέρατος κρατεῖ· τὸ δὲ ἀπειροειδὲς, ἐν ᾧ τὰ τῆς ἀπειρίας.

While we saw Proclus' establish that the two separate principles, Limit and Unlimited, were needed to explain their instantiations in Being, here Proclus seems to be claiming something broader: that in some sense even the gods themselves, as causes of their respective orders, are determined by the Limit and Unlimited. This reading is assumed by E.R. Dodds in his commentary on the *Elements*, where he says that, 'It is somewhat surprising that the henads, which are *henikôtaton* and *haploustatai*,²⁷ should be infected by this radical duality',²⁸ i.e. of Limit and Unlimited. Dodds follows the 12th-century Byzantine commentator, Nicholas of Methone, in his own interpretation of the passage, where the latter raises generally the same difficulty: 'And if there are other things [*scil.* Limit and Unlimited] which are principles of the gods, why are not these rather gods? And how are the gods composed [of limit and infinity]?'²⁹ Nicholas' reading, as well as Dodds', takes into account the first line of the proposition where Proclus says that the orders are from the 'first principles' (τῶν πρώτων ἀρχῶν) of the Limit and Unlimited—where noticeably it is *not* the gods, i.e. henads, that are the 'first principles' of those orders.³⁰ Initially this suggests that the henads within the orders are themselves composed (σύνθετοι) out of Limit and Unlimited—even though the proposition refers only to the orders, rather than the henads in themselves, as 'derived from' (ἐκ) the two principles. At first glance, Dodds and Nicholas seem to read more into the proposition than Proclus initially claims: it is the *effect* of the henads, i.e. each order, which is composed—not the henads themselves. However, if one follows *PT* III.4's position that each henad 'contains together' (συνέχει) its effect, then in this context, the henads would also 'contain together' the combination of 'limit' and 'unlimited' in their respective effects in being. One must then ask how the henads are causally coordinated with the Limit and Unlimited, if the latter two are responsible for the conditions of being limited/unlimited within each divine order.

One sees here a crucial tension, where Proclus needs two apparently distinct causal models, and not just one, to explain the emergence of Being from the One. We can sum up this tension in two points:

1. Both the henads and the Limit/Unlimited are derived from the One, but they have distinct functions and therefore different planes of influence. Are the two models identical to, or coordinated with, each other? Or are they separate?
2. Proclus seems to claim that the henads are derived from the Limit and Unlimited: even if not 'composed' in themselves, they would still imply duality by their relation to the Limit/Unlimited. Yet this would contradict their character as pure 'ones'. As a result, they should *not* be composed, let alone derived, from the two principles.

²⁷ *ET Prop.* 127.

²⁸ See commentary on Prop. 159 in Proclus (1963) 281.

²⁹ Nicholas of Methone, *Refutation* 142,29–30: καὶ εἰ τῶν θεῶν ἄλλ' ἄττα ἀρχαί, τί μὴ ἐκεῖνα μᾶλλον θεοί; καὶ πῶς σύνθετοι οἱ θεοί;

³⁰ Contrast this with *In Parm.* 1048,1–5 where Proclus directly calls the henads 'first principles' (ἀρχαί) as well.

These two points are thus inter-related: how one understands the relation between the Limit/Unlimited and the henads (1) affects how one is able to understand Proclus' claim from *ET* Prop. 159 (2).

With this in mind, we may briefly list the three positions of Cristina d'Ancona, Gerd van Riel, and Edward Butler that address (1) and attempt to solve (2):

- (i) *irreducibility* (D'Ancona's position):³¹ the Limit/Unlimited and henads are parallel but separate causal models—no relation between the two models;
- (ii) *henads-only* (Van Riel's position): the Limit/Unlimited are themselves henads, and therefore reducible to the henads' causal model; and,
- (iii) *beings-only* (Butler's position): the Limit/Unlimited are only analyzable aspects of Being, not distinct ontological entities; the henads are then the sole causal model.

As will be eventually shown, while aspects of these previous three positions are correct, there is a fourth position which resolves the tensions in (1) and (2) above: that the Limit and Unlimited are the 'first' henads, but the other, subsequent henads are determined by the Limit and Unlimited in terms of their individual character (ιδιότης). This we will consider after we first analyze D'Ancona's, Van Riel's, and Butler's positions in depth.

5. Position (i): Cristina d'Ancona

From her 1992 article, Cristina d'Ancona responds to the difficulty of Prop. 159 by suggesting that the term, 'henad', indicates two distinct kinds of entities, depending on context: either those entities determined by the Limit/Unlimited, or those derived directly from the One.³² Thus the 'henads' in Prop. 159 indicate specifically 'intelligible henads' (νοήται ἐνάδες), which receive determination from the Limit and Unlimited,³³ while other passages, like *In Parm.* 644,9–10, and *PT* III.3, 11,23–13,5, indicate specifically 'super-essential henads' (ὑπερούσιοι ἐνάδες), where they are directly derived from the One 'by unity' (καθ' ἕνωσιν).³⁴ The conflict in problem (2) only arises if the 'henads' in *ET* Prop. 159 refer to the 'super-essential' kind rather than the 'intelligible' kind, which, as intelligibles, *are* composed of limit and unlimited as elements.

D'Ancona argues for this from an analysis of the immediate context for *ET* Prop. 159. The group of propositions prior to 159—between Prop.'s. 151–156—describe the different attributes of the gods and their varying effects in lower products,³⁵ as we have already seen. Prop. 159 is then a generalization of these particular propositions, since each type of god demonstrates a variation of 'limit' or 'unlimited' (or power) in the kind of activity exercised. One can see this in a passage from the *Timaeus*

³¹ A. Sheppard (1982) 10–13 also presents this position in relation to Syrianus, who, she thinks, makes the Limit and Unlimited more significant as a causal model over the henads.

³² C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 266–267.

³³ C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 268.

³⁴ C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 269.

³⁵ C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 273.

Commentary,³⁶ where Proclus directly connects the attributes of the gods to the general attributes of 'limit' and 'unlimited':

Among the gods themselves, some belong to the column of the Limit, others to that of the Unlimited, both as whole classes and as individuals (κατὰ μέρη):³⁷ as whole classes because the entire paternal, maintaining, and creative series is defined by Limit, the entire zoogenic and generative series by the Unlimited; as individuals because, within both the paternal and the zoogenic series, some [gods] are on the side of one of these principles, others on the side of the other. So if this is the situation even among the gods, is it any wonder if among the Forms too some are more akin to Limit than the rest, others more akin to the Unlimited [...]? (*In Tim.* I, 441,3–12; trans. Runia/Share, modified)

καὶ γὰρ αὐτῶν τῶν θεῶν οἱ μὲν εἰσι τῆς τοῦ πέρατος συστοιχίας, οἱ δὲ τῆς τοῦ ἀπείρου, καθ' ὅλας τε διακοσμήσεις καὶ κατὰ μέρη· καθ' ὅλας μὲν, ὅτι πᾶσα ἡ πατρικὴ καὶ συνοχικὴ καὶ δημιουργικὴ σειρὰ κατὰ τὸ πέρασ ἀφορίζεται, πᾶσα δὲ ἡ ζωογόνος καὶ γεννητικὴ κατὰ τὸ ἄπειρον· κατὰ μέρη δέ, ὅτι καὶ τῆς πατρικῆς καὶ τῆς ζωογονικῆς οἱ μὲν εἰσι πρὸς τῆσδε τῆς ἀρχῆς, οἱ δὲ πρὸς τῆς ἑτέρας. εἰ τοίνυν καὶ ἐπὶ θεῶν οὕτως, τί θαυμαστόν, εἰ καὶ τῶν εἰδῶν τὰ μὲν ἔστι τοῦ πέρατος, τὰ δὲ τῆς ἀπειρίας συγγενῆ μάλλον τῶν ἑτέρων...;

As D'Ancona notes, the attributes listed in this passage are paralleled in *ET Prop.*'s. 151–158.³⁸ The listing of these functions for the gods follows different modes of production from the Limit and Unlimited, as the *Timaeus Commentary* passage draws out the relations of certain attributes to either the limit (e.g. 'paternal', 'conservative', etc.) or the unlimited (e.g. 'demiurgic', 'vivifying', etc.).³⁹ Insofar as the gods and Forms parallel each other, where both show the effects of either the Limit and Unlimited in their activity, there is a correlation between the two classes. D'Ancona emphasizes this parallel by pointing to *In Parm.* 909,1–36, where every divine Form (θεῖον εἶδος) possesses the same characteristics as those mentioned in the *Elements* and *Timaeus Commentary* passages.⁴⁰ In the *Parmenides Commentary* passage only the Forms, rather than the gods or henads, have the characteristics that are derived from the principles of Limit and Unlimited. This would fall in line with the claim in *ET Prop.* 89 that all 'real being' (τὸ ὄντως ὄν) is composed of 'limit' and 'unlimited', insofar as the Forms are constitutive of the realm of true being. On this reading, the principles of Limit and Unlimited only act on the entities constituting 'real being', rather than the super-essential henads.

D'Ancona next references *PT III.12* where Proclus identifies the Limit, Unlimited, and the Mixed as the first triad of intelligibles.⁴¹ By implication the generation of the gods are related to the Limit and Unlimited, taken as intelligibles, where the Mixed represents the highest of the intelligibles

³⁶ Here onward abbreviated '*In Tim.*'

³⁷ Lit. 'by part'; D'Ancona translates as 'per i singoli'. Although see discussion below in Positions (iii) and (iv).

³⁸ C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 273.

³⁹ Cf. C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 273–275, who references Syrianus' commentary on Aristotle's *Metaphysics M* as a background source and elaboration for Proclus' discussion.

⁴⁰ C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 277.

⁴¹ *PT III.12*, 44,21–45,12. Cf. C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 275.

generated.⁴² This suggests that the gods which are derived from the Limit and Unlimited—i.e. the henads of Prop’s. 151–159—are intelligible and in the realm of being. Thanks to this implicit identification of the gods with the intelligible realm, alongside the convertibility of attributes between the gods and Forms, D’Ancona concludes that the ‘henads’ determined by the Limit and Unlimited correlate to the intelligible gods.⁴³

For the second sense of ‘henads’ as super-essential, D’Ancona focuses on their distinct causal role compared to the Limit and Unlimited. Whereas the latter explain the dual aspects of determination and indetermination, or variations of unity and power, which are found in all beings, the super-essential henads explain the unique character (*ιδιότης*) found in a given chain of entities or Forms. They function as breaks for an infinite regress of causes for the character that they produce, since each is a pure unity and not unified by some higher cause.⁴⁴ In this role, the henads are properly first principles (*ἀρχαί*) for the character they generate in an order of entities, including the Forms, since they pre-contain that character in their mode of unity.⁴⁵ By contrast, the Limit and Unlimited do not explain the character or ‘content’ of the Forms, but rather the characteristics, or genus, of being (*γενή τοῦ ὄντος*).⁴⁶ One can detect here the Plotinian legacy of the *megista genê* from the *Sophist* as explaining Intellect’s internal makeup, where it is characterized by simultaneous unity and multiplicity. Proclus links this trait to the interaction of the two principles, albeit where the two elements are *external* to Being and Intellect, rather than internal to Intellect for Plotinus. The Limit and Unlimited are then responsible for the ‘determination–indetermination’ conditions that the Forms have with each other,⁴⁷ while the super-essential henads explain the specific ‘content’ of each Form in itself.

From this analysis, D’Ancona distinguishes three references for the term, ‘henad’:

- (H₁), applied to the Limit and Unlimited themselves (e.g. *PT* III.9);
- (H₂), applied to the entities derived from the Limit/Unlimited (*ET* Prop. 159); and,
- (H₃), applied to the entities directly derived from the One ‘by unity’ (*καθ’ ἑνωσιν*) (e.g. *In Parm.* 644,9–10; *PT* III.3).

As we have seen, D’Ancona indicates (H₂) and (H₃) as pertaining to opposed kinds of entities: (H₂) as the intelligible gods, and therefore in the category of being, and (H₃) as the entities beyond being. The ontological status of (H₁) is not entirely clear, especially whether (H₁) can be identified with (H₃) (as Van Riel and Combès do so, for instance). Yet in her paper’s conclusion, D’Ancona appears to confirm an identification of (H₁) with (H₃) as ‘supreme henads’ inasmuch as the super-essential henads (H₃) are ‘distributed’ in an order subsequent to the Limit and Unlimited’s derivation of the differing order of

⁴² C. D’Ancona Costa (1992) 276.

⁴³ C. D’Ancona Costa (1992) 279.

⁴⁴ C. D’Ancona Costa (1992) 285. See *ET* Prop. 6 and *In Parm.* 1219,22 ff.

⁴⁵ C. D’Ancona Costa (1992) 286–287. See also *ET* Prop. 118.

⁴⁶ C. D’Ancona Costa (1992) 286.

⁴⁷ C. D’Ancona Costa (1992) 287.

intelligibles (H₂).⁴⁸ One way to construe this would be that the henads are positioned, as it were, *after* the structure of the different levels/orders of intelligibles are produced by the Limit and Unlimited. This does not imply that the Limit/Unlimited *directly* determine the henads, although the latter are *indirectly* determined inasmuch as they are placed over specific intelligibles that have already been determined. Ultimately whether or how (H₁) and (H₃) are coordinated is unclear in Proclus' account, for D'Ancona, and one reason that the tension remains unsolved in his framework.

Given our analysis, one problem with D'Ancona's interpretation is that her reading of *ET* Prop. 159 does not account for Proclus' restriction of the term, 'god', only to separately existing entities (H₃) in *ET* Prop. 114. There, Proclus references the earlier Prop. 64, where every monad which is a principle (ἀρχική μόνως) produces two kinds of entities: (1) immanent properties, or 'irradiations' (ἐλλάμψεις), and (2) separately existing, self-complete entities (αὐτοτελεῖς ὑποστάσεις). Proclus explicitly refers to these two senses for henads in Prop. 64, while in Prop's. 113–165 on the henads, he often narrows the scope to just (2) when he references the 'gods' specifically. D'Ancona's 'intelligible henads' (νοῦται ἐνάδες) would then have to refer to sense (1) as composed entities, whereas the henads-proper (2) are not such. However this does not address the problem with *ET* Prop. 159 that it is the orders of gods, as 'self-complete existences', that are implicitly derived from the Limit and Unlimited—in other words (H₃).⁴⁹ Nevertheless, D'Ancona's distinction between the use of the term, 'henad', for the Limit/Unlimited (H₁) compared to the super-essential henads (H₃) is important to delineate the distinct causal functions both play, as will be brought out again for Position (iv), below.

6. Position (ii): Gerd Van Riel

On Gerd Van Riel's reading from his 2001 article, the Limit and Unlimited are both (a) henads, and (b) paradigmatic instantiations of the henads' two attributes of subsistence (ὑπαρξίς) and power (δύναμις):⁵⁰ in his phrasing, each henad is a 'modality' or instantiation of the Limit (πέρας), while the variation in each henad's internal power, which corresponds to differing effects, is an instantiation of the Unlimited (ἀπειρία). On this reading, *ET* Prop. 159 does not imply composition in the henads by the two principles, but rather indicates descriptively the henads' internal attributes of the ὑπαρξίς and δύναμις, which correlate to the Limit and Unlimited respectively.

Van Riel makes his point by emphasizing the lack of 'real distinction' that exists between the Limit and Unlimited, since they always appear together at all levels of being up to the co-existence of the two principles in themselves.⁵¹ For his thesis Van Riel draws from *PT* III.8, 31,14–32,7 and III.14, 51,6–7, where

⁴⁸ C. D'Ancona Costa (1992) 293. Implicitly she seems to agree with G. Van Riel (2001), discussed below.

⁴⁹ As well, D'Ancona's passage, *In Tim.* I, 441,3–14, suggests that the gods (2) *individually* as well as according to their orders are determined by Limit and Unlimited.

⁵⁰ Others like J. Combès (1996) (251–3), J. Trouillard (1977) (102), and Westerink–Saffrey in their commentary on *PT* III (LVIII–LIX) advance a basic version of Van Riel's thesis in identifying the Limit/Unlimited as primitive henads. S. Gersh (2014) 46, n. 62, critiques Van Riel's approach as too complicated and 'has no textual basis in [*PT*] or elsewhere in Proclus', although Van Riel appears to reconstruct such a position in his 421, n. 22.

⁵¹ G. Van Riel (2001) 427–428.

the Limit⁵² is explicitly referred to as a henad.⁵³ In *PT* III.14, Proclus places the Limit as the first term of the first intelligible triad, while the Unlimited (ἀπειρία) and the ‘Mixed’ (μικτόν) make up the corresponding second and third terms. ‘Limit’ in this case then implies ‘henad and subsistence’ (ἐνάς και ὑπαρξίς) in relation to the Unlimited as the corresponding ‘power’ (δύναμις) and the Mixed as ‘Being, Life, and intelligible intellect’ (οὐσία και ζωή και νοῦς νοητός). The Unlimited then becomes an intermediate link between the Limit and its product, the Mixed. *PT* III.8 justifies this link by proving that the Limit, while a ‘particular one’ (τι ἕν), cannot bring Being into existence without possessing a generative power—thus the Unlimited.⁵⁴ The Limit and Unlimited are then closely linked to each other in the causal process of generating Being, so that the Limit, as the first term of the triad, ‘comporte en soi, sans que ceci n’introduise une différenciation, Ἰἀπειρία (sa force génératrice)’. Whereas *ET* Prop. 90 demonstrated that the Limit and Unlimited exist as opposed, separate principles, the passages cited by Van Riel suggest the opposite—that the Limit implies the Unlimited in itself, and not as opposed to or separate from the Unlimited.⁵⁵

Van Riel’s claim is supported by the fact that Proclus calls the Limit and Unlimited henads, as we have seen, which do not imply any difference and are unqualifiedly ‘all in all’ (πάσαι ἐν πάσαις). This would also support Van Riel’s suggestion that the Unlimited is ‘in’ the Limit as the power of the Limit, or of every henad considered as an instantiation of the Limit.⁵⁶ While there is no ontological difference between henads, what distinguishes each henad is only the unique character (ιδιότης) pertaining to each—one aspect alongside unity (ἕνωσις) which constitutes the ‘*existentialia*’ of the henads.⁵⁷ Although not made explicit by Van Riel, the Limit and Unlimited would then name two characters, or ιδιότητες, corresponding to the first two, respective henads that come forth from the One. Consequently the Limit is the first, primary henad, paradigmatic of the henads’ subsistence (ὑπαρξίς), and the Unlimited is the paradigmatic manifestation of the henads’ generative power (δύναμις). The Unlimited would then be an externalization of the Limit’s internal power, just like all henads which imply their own internal power. The causal structure for the two principles is repeated for all subsequent henads, albeit without each henad’s internal power manifesting separately as with the Unlimited.⁵⁸

Given this reading, one problem with Van Riel’s approach is that it does not substantively engage with *ET* Prop. 159 or with the prior Prop’s. 151–158 (as we saw in D’Ancona), especially since his paper opens up as a restatement on Dodds’ and Nicholas’ objection over Prop. 159. As mentioned earlier, Van Riel’s

⁵² G. Van Riel (2001) 428, n. 68, which refers to *PT* III.9, 36,12–15 making the explicit identification of the Limit and Unlimited as henads.

⁵³ G. Van Riel (2001) 427.

⁵⁴ See also *PT* III.24, 85,5. Cf. G. Van Riel (2001) 424–5.

⁵⁵ Thus, even though there are references to a ‘Limit-itself’ (*autoperas*) and ‘Unlimited-itself’ (*autoapeiria*), ‘Ἰἀπειρία ne se manifeste jamais en séparation du πέρας, et que, vu l’unité absolue à ce niveau de la réalité, les deux principes ne sont pas réellement différents’ (G. Van Riel (2001) 427).

⁵⁶ G. Van Riel (2001) 424.

⁵⁷ G. Van Riel (2001) 424. However cf. E. Butler (2008b) 142, discussed below, who disagrees on such a distinction.

⁵⁸ G. Van Riel (2001) 428–429.

solution seems to read Prop. 159 as *not* saying that the Limit and Unlimited act on the henads—or that the henads are ‘composed’—but rather that the henads’ derivation from the Limit and Unlimited merely indicates the two aspects of each henad’s subsistence (ὑπαρξις) and power (δύναμις). Van Riel, however, does not address whether the Limit and Unlimited actually do act on the henads or whether the two have some coordinated role with the One’s derivation of the henads. On the one hand, by affirming that the Limit and Unlimited correspond to the dual aspects of the henads, the problem of the henads’ composition is resolved, since each henad’s subsistence and power exist without distinction according to the henad’s unity.⁵⁹ However if we consider the heading of *ET* Prop. 159 with that of *ET* Prop. 89, essentially the same kind of derivation is implied: for Prop. 89, ‘Every real being is *derived from* (ἐκ) limit and unlimited’ (πάν τὸ ὄντως ὄν ἐκ πέρατός ἐστι καὶ ἀπειρου); and for Prop. 159, ‘Every order of gods is *derived from* (ἐκ) the first principles, limit and unlimitedness’ (πάσα τάξις θεῶν ἐκ τῶν πρώτων ἐστὶν ἀρχῶν, πέρατος καὶ ἀπειρίας). Where Prop. 89 clearly implies composition for ‘real Being’ (τὸ ὄντως ὄν), one could easily read Prop. 159 in the same way. The latter in fact more strongly implies a differentiation of the Limit and Unlimited in relation to the henads, since the former are called ‘first principles’. By referring the ‘orders of gods’, and by proxy the henads, towards first principles which are the Limit and Unlimited, the causal reading for ἐκ cannot be ruled out—and thereby Nicholas of Methone’s question still remains.

An additional problem for Van Riel’s reading is that it makes the Limit and Unlimited henads in the same sense as the ‘henads’ considered in Prop. 159, which suggests a double instantiation of ‘limit’ and ‘unlimited’ in each of them. In other words, if each henad implies its internal, corresponding aspects of ‘limit’ and ‘unlimited’, then the Limit as a henad would also instantiate itself in terms of its own aspect of ‘limit’, and so the same for the Unlimited with its own aspect of the ‘unlimited’. In both cases this would imply a vicious circle. Furthermore we should recall that *ET* Prop. 90 emphasizes the opposed relation that exists between the Limit and Unlimited: ‘It is necessary that the first Unlimited is without the form of limit, and that the first Limit is without the form of the unlimited.’⁶⁰ Yet if the Limit and Unlimited are henads, then both imply the internal properties of ‘subsistence’ (correlating to ‘limit’) and ‘power’ (correlating to ‘unlimited’)—which this passage seems to deny. One possible alternative would be to affirm that the ‘form of limit’ (περατοειδές) and ‘form of unlimited’ (ἀπειροειδές) only indicate the particular characters (ιδιότητες) that differentiate the Limit and Unlimited as henads, rather than the internal structure of ‘subsistence’ and ‘power’ that all henads share. If so, then Van Riel’s claim that the Limit and Unlimited are paradigmatic henads needs to be qualified, especially in light of passages like *ET* Prop. 90 that assert the opposed relation between the two principles.

⁵⁹ Cf. *ET* Prop’s. 118, 121.

⁶⁰ *ET* Prop. 90, 82,14–15: οὐκ ἄρα δεῖ περατοειδές εἶναι τὸ πρώτως ἀπειρον καὶ ἀπειροειδές τὸ πρώτον πέρας. Juxtaposed with this are passages like *PT* III.14, 51,3–7, which suggest that the Unlimited proceeds forth as a middle term from the Limit and establishes a relationship (σχέσις) between the Limit and the ‘Mixed’/Being. Yet this suggests that the Unlimited is *not* opposed, as the Mixed is to the Limit, implying that the Limit pre-contains the Unlimited.

A final problem with this reading is that it is not clear why the Limit and Unlimited are needed as distinct causes:⁶¹ if the henads fulfill the function of these two principles within themselves, what distinct role do the Limit and Unlimited possess beyond being the first henads after the One? Given the passages we have seen where Proclus gives a distinct consideration to the Limit and Unlimited as principles explaining a specific set of features that henads do not cover—as we saw in Position (i), above—we should at least be cautious to take the Limit and Unlimited as equally ‘henads’ in the same sense as all others. This is an issue we will return to below in Position (iii) and finally in (iv).

7. Position (iii): Edward Butler

For Edward Butler, the Limit and Unlimited are aspects of the henads, as in Van Riel’s reading, however the two terms do not indicate separate principles as for Van Riel, but are ‘analytical concepts’ from the perspective of Being.⁶² Thus, Problem (1) is dealt with by denying that the Limit and Unlimited constitute a distinct causal model—since they only indicate the henads’ causal activity—while problem (2) is settled similarly to Van Riel’s interpretation⁶³ insofar as the ‘limit’ and ‘unlimited’ in *ET* Prop. 159 only indicate the henads’ ὑπαρξίς and δύναμις. In this, Butler’s reading is concomitant with his overall position that the henads are the sole first principles over Being, which follows on his view that the ‘One-itself’ (τὸ αὐτοέν) does not exist as a separate principle, but is *simply* the henads.⁶⁴

In this respect, Butler does not see the henads as deriving from the One in any sense analogous to the causal procession of the lower levels of Being, as in Van Riel’s and (implicitly) D’Ancona’s frameworks, but instead they stand as autonomous individuals that are principles of both universals and particulars. Butler here puts weight on passages where Proclus emphasizes the unity of the henads collectively, where they are entirely ‘all in all’ (πάσαι ἐν πάσαις) unlike the Forms and lower levels of being:⁶⁵ since they transcend the kind of distinction entailed by ‘sameness’ and ‘difference’ at the level of Being, the henads are equally ‘one’—taken together and in themselves—as they are equally ‘many’—taken as unitary individuals. Consequently for Butler, a sharply distinct logic from that of Being obtains at the henads’ level: one cannot quantify the henads in themselves or make a distinction between ‘the One’ and ‘the henads’—whether real or virtual.⁶⁶ The henads are then only classified in their activity within Being: when Proclus, for instance, refers to the intelligible triad of the ‘Limit’, ‘Unlimited’, and Mixed (or Being), this ultimately describes *each* henad (or god) and its effect, where the ‘Limit’ indicates the god in itself, and the ‘Unlimited’ the emerging activity of that god upon Being,

⁶¹ As we will see next, Butler seems to follow this intuition in denying that the Limit/Unlimited are separate principles.

⁶² E. Butler (2003) 391–392.

⁶³ Although see E. Butler (2008b) 142, discussed below.

⁶⁴ E. Butler (2005) 97–98. Discussed below.

⁶⁵ Cf. e.g. *In Parm.* 1049,1–2.

⁶⁶ In this sense, ‘the One’ as an unparticipated source for the henads, for Butler, would only be rationally distinct, as it were: whereas the henads differ from each other virtually, if not really, this sense does not obtain for Butler’s ‘One’. On this see E. Butler (2003) 168–169.

or the intelligible.⁶⁷ In turn, then, the intelligible triad is taken to represent all the henads in their unity, while the subsequent second triad (the intelligible-intellective) and the third triad (the intellective) each progressively reveal increasing distinctinctions in the kinds of henads in their causality.⁶⁸ Consequently the ‘Unlimited’ becomes a placeholder for a henad’s power (δύναμις), and thus for Butler: “Powers”, when taken in this fashion as properties of unique individuals, yield kinds, and therefore they both express the uniqueness of an individual and also embody the negation of that very uniqueness; hence their mediating role in the first intelligible triad.⁶⁹

One can then see why Butler disagrees with Van Riel on the henads’ ιδιότης: whereas for Van Riel it is ‘une caractéristique typique’ distinct from a given henad’s subsistence (ὑπαρξίς) as ‘one’,⁷⁰ Butler disagrees, maintaining that the ιδιότης is a ‘unique individuating character’ which is identical with the henad’s ὑπαρξίς/subsistence.⁷¹ For Butler, Van Riel’s distinction fails to consider the indeterminacy of the number of gods in Proclus’ scheme, while identifiable ‘types’ are only determined from the level of Being: thus any number of gods can become associated with a given ‘type’ or class of being, and not just one particular god to a specific ‘type’. In turn, the specific ιδιότης differentiating each god can only be determined within particular theological frameworks associated with those specific gods, and not from within the domain of Being.⁷² One then cannot identify the ιδιότητες of the henads with specific classes or orders in Being: instead the ιδιότητες of the henads are the basis for the orders and principles of Being—including apparently distinct principles like the Limit and Unlimited—and thus cannot be related to any class of Being.

From here we can see why Butler claims that ‘there is no such thing as the One Itself, if we mean something different than the henads; Godhood is nothing but the Gods themselves.’⁷³ We have already seen the groundwork set for Butler’s claim here, inasmuch as the horizon between the henads, among themselves and in relation to the ‘One’ (or generically pure unity), is flattened. In following this intuition, the One as ‘unparticipated’ only refers to the henads’ mode of subsistence as unities, which Butler argues from Proclus’ characterization of the One compared to other unparticipated monads in the lower levels of being: where the latter produce entities by diminution (καθ’ ὑπόβασιν) or procession (κατὰ πρόοδον), the One only does so ‘by unity’ (καθ’ ἔνωσιν), beyond the sameness or difference implied in the other kinds of production.⁷⁴ The henads cannot then be ‘subordinated’ under the One in

⁶⁷ E. Butler (2008b) 134.

⁶⁸ E. Butler (2008b) 135. For a thorough, enlightening discussion of the second/intelligible–intellective and third/intellective triads as resulting from the different stages of the henads’ relation to themselves and towards each other, see E. Butler (2010) (esp. 141–142) and E. Butler (2012). One can see with these Butler’s systematic reading following on his emphasis of the henads as the primary, if sole, locus for the ἀρχή of all beings.

⁶⁹ E. Butler (2008b) 136; see also further 137–138.

⁷⁰ G. Van Riel (2001) 424.

⁷¹ E. Butler (2008b) 142.

⁷² E.g. the Greek pantheon, or the Egyptian sets of gods, etc.: cf. E. Butler (2008b) 142.

⁷³ E. Butler (2008a) 98.

⁷⁴ E. Butler (2003) 168–169. Cf. *In Parm.* 745,14–746,9.

the same way as other, lower beings which come under a given unparticipated monad, since the henads are equally ‘one’ as the One-itself.⁷⁵ On Butler’s interpretation, this means two alternatives: either the One exists separately and therefore has priority over the henads—which runs contrary to the henads’ procession from the One καθ’ ἑνωσιν—or, the only possible alternative, the One must be identical to the henads. As a result ‘the One’ indicates the henads’ subsistence (ὑπαρξίς), taken by itself without referring to any one or other particular henad, while when not referring to any of the henads, it has no existence in *any* respect.⁷⁶ One could re-formulate this along Aristotelian lines, where the henads are primary—like the category of primary substance in Aristotle’s *Categories*—while the ‘One’ is only instantiated as each henad’s ὑπαρξίς—like the *Categories*’ secondary substance. In this respect, Butler’s reading of the ‘One’ is similar to his interpretation of the Limit/Unlimited, where both indicate aspects, not distinct principles: the former as regarding the henads’ subsistence (ὑπαρξίς), and the latter as regarding the henads in their activity and power (δύναμις). We can see here Butler’s framework thus following on his stance that the ἀρχή of all things can *only* refer to the henads, collectively, as autonomous individuals from which all things proceed. Consequently, since there is no hierarchical ordering between the henads, among themselves or from one source like the ‘One’, one need not posit the Limit/Unlimited as distinct principles to explain any distinction among them or in their effects in being.

The virtue of Butler’s reading is that it systematically tackles Proclus’ understanding of the henads as absolutely singular individuals, where their activity collectively brings about unity and plurality within being—starting with the unity of Being-itself. In turn, Butler’s reading has the benefit of explaining passages where Proclus speaks of both the Limit and Unlimited producing Being (e.g. *PT* III.9, 36,10–19), while he also speaks of Being as that which ‘has received a plurality of henads and powers’ (πλήθος ἐνάδων καὶ δυνάμεων...ὑποεξάμενον) (40,7–8). On Butler’s reading of 36,10–19, the Limit/Unlimited are then aspects expressing each henad’s activity, so that the later 40,7–8 is descriptive of Being as a result of *all* the henads’ activity producing the first effect, Being-itself.⁷⁷ Butler’s framework thus addresses Dodds’ and Nicholas of Methone’s concern of ‘composition’ in the henads, since the henads simply *are* the ‘One’ and need not be derived from a distinct source—the main problematic that Van Riel’s and D’Ancona’s frameworks maintain in their solutions.

Given this, two difficulties arise in Butler’s account. One is his reductive reading of Proclus’ One-itself (τὸ αὐτόεν) to indicate each henad’s ὑπαρξίς as ‘one’, where the henads’ being ‘all in all’ (πάσαι ἐν πάσαις) symbolizes this unity.⁷⁸ Yet in passages such as *PT* III.4, when addressing the One and the henads’ status, Proclus appears to appeal to the One as a distinct principle in the causal process of the henads: ‘And in this way all things tend up to the very first cause of the universe: dissimilars through similars, and similars through themselves’ (καὶ πάντα οὕτως εἰς τὸ πρώτιστον ἀνατείνεται τῶν ὄλων αἴτιον, τὰ μὲν ἀνόμοια διὰ τῶν ὁμοίων, τὰ δὲ ὁμοια δι’ ἑαυτῶν) (16,5–7). In passages like this, Proclus seems to maintain the ‘very first cause’ (implicitly the One) as a distinct principle from the ‘similars’ (implicitly the henads) by reference to which the henads exercise their causality ‘through themselves’. Thus when

⁷⁵ E. Butler (2008a) 97–98; see also in general E. Butler (2005).

⁷⁶ E. Butler (2008a) 98–99.

⁷⁷ Cf. E. Butler (2010) 155

⁷⁸ E. Butler (2008a) 98, 101–103. Cf. E. Butler (2005), esp. 83–84 and 97–98.

transposing Butler's framework onto this passage, it is not clear how the henads' unity—whether taken individually as the ὑπαρξις of each, or (also) as the unity of henads altogether—can take over the One's capacity as a distinct point of reference for their causality. In this light, it is not apparent why one cannot still posit the One in the manner of another 'henad', as it were, alongside the other henads/gods, whose ιδιότης is itself not to be participated as the other henads are.⁷⁹ Such a position would do justice to the language of *PT* III.4 without 'hypostatizing' the One or subordinating the henads in their unity and function as the causal loci of Being.⁸⁰

A second difficulty, which Eric Perl discusses well, is that Butler's framework asserts the 'facticity' of the henads, only discoverable through revelation from particular gods or their particular theological frameworks, without recourse to a philosophical ground such as the 'One' in the way just described.⁸¹ As Perl points out, Proclus in *ET* Prop. 123—apparently in contrast to Butler's position—claims that 'from the things that are dependent on [the gods], their unique characters (ιδιότητες) are made known ... For the differences of the participants are distinguished along with the unique characters of the participated'.⁸² Whereas Butler strongly distinguishes ιδιότης from the 'types' pertaining to beings, Proclus here appears to indicate exactly this—that one can determine a god's ιδιότης from its participants. On the one hand, one may concur with Butler that the ιδιότης pertaining to certain gods, as (e.g.) Zeus or Rhea among the Greek pantheon, cannot be discerned directly from the types of being (even though their *power/δύναμις* in causality can). Yet passages like the above suggest a more blurred interpretation: either that ιδιότης implies certain 'henads' in themselves, such as the Limit/Unlimited from *PT* III.9, or it implies Butler's interpretation of δύναμις as the link between each henad and Being (thus Zeus and Rhea in their respective causal activity). In either case this appears to reflect an ambivalence in Proclus' use of the term, while passages like Prop. 123 support Van Riel's interpretation of ιδιότης as a 'une caractéristique typique'.

Both these tensions suggest, first, the need to preserve the One (τὸ αὐτοῦν) as distinct from the henads—while accepting Butler's claim that the henads are the primary, if sole, causal locus for Being's emergence; and second, in light of passages like Prop. 123, that Van Riel's interpretation of the Limit/Unlimited should still be preserved: namely where the two indicate each henad, *and* two first, distinct henads after the One. Thus while one may follow Butler's reading of the interplay of the henads' causal activity in the intelligible triad, one can also consider the Limit/Unlimited as distinct henads which also pre-figure the activity of all the henads—as in Van Riel's position. How the two interact with each other we must next see.

⁷⁹ On this critique/alternative suggested, see D. MacIsaac (2007) 148, n. 27.

⁸⁰ Cf. E. Butler (2008a) 98–99 and esp. E. Butler (2010) 154, where the unity of Intellect (and Being in general) is the result of 'a coming-together of really autarchic individuals, and not through the parcelling out of a pre-existing, presupposed unity—a falsely hypostatized unity'. In turn, see the critique of E. Perl (2010) 183.

⁸¹ E. Butler (2008a) 109, 111. Cf. E. Perl (2010) 182–183, including n. 53 which compares Butler's position with Plotinus' *Enn.* VI.8.7–10, which critiques a similar claim for the first principle (or principles) as 'happening to be'.

⁸² 110,4–7: ἀλλ' ἀπὸ τῶν ἐξηρητημένων οἰαί πέρ εἰσιν αὐτῶν αἱ ιδιότητες γνωρίζονται ... κατὰ γὰρ τὰς τῶν μετεχομένων ιδιότητας καὶ αἱ τῶν μετεχόντων συνδιαιροῦνται διαφορόντες. See also *In Parm.* 1049,7–22, which elaborates this notion. Cf. E. Perl (2010) 183–184.

8. A New Solution? Position (iv)

In reviewing these three positions, the main *aporia* one keeps finding is the tension between, on the one hand, the claim that the henads are causally derived from the principles of the Limit/Unlimited,⁸³ and, on the other hand, the claim that the henads' nature is pure unity—which implies that they cannot be so 'derived'. As we have seen from Van Riel's and Butler's positions, Proclus' framework still suggests, first, two distinct principles correlated to the aspects of 'limit' and 'unlimited' found within the henads in their causality; and second, that those two principles have a causal role in regards to those two aspects. With this last notion in mind, we should analyze more closely how these two principles, as Limit- and Unlimited-itself, relate to all other henads.

As we have seen, what characterizes the henads are (a) their subsistence (ὑπαρξις) as purely 'one', and (b) the unique character (ιδιότης) by which each is positively differentiated in relation to the other. While neither (a) nor (b) constitutes a 'real' difference in the henads,⁸⁴ the unique character of each henad is nevertheless made manifest within the henads' respective participants—following from *ET Prop.* 123. Inasmuch as each henad's character is manifested at the different levels of Being, one can say that that henad pre-contains its differentiated effects according its own unity—which is also its unique character.⁸⁵ Thus, while each henad is simply unity καθ' ὑπαρξιν, each is also that specific feature of Being κατ' αὐτίαν, inasmuch as a given henad's character is the basis on which it produces its differentiated effect.⁸⁶

This background contextualizes *ET Prop.*'s. 151–158 which describe the orders of gods according to different hierarchical grades, as 'paternal', 'generative', and so on. The 'orders' then depend on the commonality shared between the unique characters of the respective sets of henads in their causal activity—while each henad, by itself, does not share any commonality or characteristics with any other. Although the 'orders of gods' describe the effects that come after the henads, the orders must ultimately be grounded in the collective ιδιότητες of the henads: a henad that belongs to the 'generative' order must have that attribute as part of its ιδιότης, whereas a henad of the 'paternal' order must also have that attribute as part of its ιδιότης. Thus, while both henads by their subsistence do not have any relation with each other, they are determined in relation to each other by their ιδιότης.⁸⁷

⁸³ D. O'Meara (1989) 138–141 discusses how Proclus' predecessor, Iamblichus, subscribes to this model exactly with his notion of 'divine numbers' derived from the Limit/Unlimited. As O'Meara notes, Proclus appears to distance himself from this approach in order to emphasize, e.g., the autonomy of the henads as gods (a point well made by Butler).

⁸⁴ Cf. G. Van Riel (2001) 427–428, discussed earlier. See also *In Parm.* 1049,26–27 which contrasts the unity (ἕνωσιν) and unique characters (ιδιότητα) of the henads with the lower analogues of sameness (ταυτότητος) and difference (ἐτερότητος) belonging to beings.

⁸⁵ Cf. E. Butler (2008b) 133–134, including n. 4, who highlights the internal tension between the henad's transcendence (as 'one') and its illumination of Being.

⁸⁶ Cf. *ET Prop.* 118, esp. 104,5,–7, where each henad pre-contains its effect according to its character (ιδιότης) which is 'unitary' (ἐνιαίως), implicitly its ὑπαρξις.

⁸⁷ Cf. *In Parm.* 936 ff. where Proclus discusses how the henads relate to each other inasmuch as they depend solely on themselves.

This point is brought out when we look again at *ET* Prop. 159: if the orders of gods are derived ($\acute{\epsilon}\kappa$) from the Limit and Unlimited, by proxy the $\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\tau}\textit{\epsilon}\textit{\varsigma}}$ of the henads must also be coordinated with—and in this sense, determined by—the Limit and Unlimited. D’Ancona’s reference to *In Tim.* I, 441,3–14 confirms this, where Proclus specifies that the Limit/Unlimited determine the henads both as whole classes and $\text{\textit{\kappa}\textit{\alpha}\textit{\tau}\textit{\acute{\alpha}}\ \textit{\mu}\textit{\acute{\epsilon}}\textit{\rho}\textit{\eta}}$. Although the term is ambiguous here—whether Proclus has in mind *particular* henads or *traits* belonging to particular henads⁸⁸—the overarching context suggests that the particular character ($\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\varsigma}}$) pertaining to each henad, in its causal relation to Being, is what is determined.

At the same time, we should be cautious: in acknowledging Butler’s observation on the henads’ nature, we do not want to say that the Limit/Unlimited causally act on the henads in ‘determining’ their $\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\tau}\textit{\alpha}}$, in the sense that they would be subordinated. We may then modify our description of the interaction in the following way: in discussing Butler, we concluded that one could conceive of the One as a ‘point of reference’, and as a ground in this sense, by which each henad in its unity and causality functions. We could also render the henads’ relation to the Limit and Unlimited similarly: the Limit/Unlimited as distinct principles are together the point of reference and ground for the varying traits of ‘limit’ and ‘unlimited’ found in each henad’s $\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\varsigma}}$. Phrased this way, this respects the identification of each henad’s $\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\varsigma}}$ with its $\text{\textit{\upsilon}\textit{\pi}\textit{\alpha}\textit{\rho}\textit{\xi}\textit{\iota}\textit{\varsigma}}$ —reflecting the henads’ unity and autonomy—while acknowledging distinct ‘sources’: the One for each henad’s $\text{\textit{\upsilon}\textit{\pi}\textit{\alpha}\textit{\rho}\textit{\xi}\textit{\iota}\textit{\varsigma}}$ as ‘one’, and the Limit/Unlimited for each henad’s $\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\varsigma}}$ as implying the combination of ‘limit’ and ‘unlimited’ unfolded in Being.

Put this way, the worry behind Dodds’ and Nicholas of Methone’s concern (i.e. Problem [2]) disappears: the Limit and Unlimited determine the henads’ character ($\text{\textit{\iota}\textit{\delta}\textit{\iota}\textit{\omicron}\textit{\tau}\textit{\eta}\textit{\varsigma}}$), in the sense described above, rather than their subsistence ($\text{\textit{\upsilon}\textit{\pi}\textit{\alpha}\textit{\rho}\textit{\xi}\textit{\iota}\textit{\varsigma}}$) as ‘one’, where that character anticipates the differentiated composition of ‘limit’ and ‘unlimited’ in the henad’s respective effect in Being.⁸⁹ This concurs with D’Ancona’s reading that the Limit/Unlimited properly act on beings (her distinction [H2]) rather than the henads *per se* (her [H3]), inasmuch as the two principles are those by which the henads, through their varying characters, produce and act on beings. Similarly Van Riel’s reading helps to show how the Limit and Unlimited emerge as the first henads from the One, as seen in *PT* III.9, where they establish the dynamic of ‘limit’/‘unlimited’ in their respective causality within Being.

On this interpretation, the henads’ emergence from the One, with the various stages of the production of Being, proceeds in coordination with the Limit and Unlimited as the ‘first’ henads to emerge before subsequent henads emerge. In this capacity, the Limit/Unlimited then act both as the first henads producing Being, *and* as the ground on which the varying characters of subsequent henads anticipate and produce the differing combinations of ‘limit’/‘unlimited’ in all subsequent regions of Being.

⁸⁸ I.e., to take the Greek term literally, ‘by part [of each class]’; although note, earlier in *In Tim.* 439,22–440,28, Proclus also uses $\text{\textit{\mu}\textit{\acute{\epsilon}}\textit{\rho}\textit{\eta}}$ to refer to enmattered particulars, in juxtaposing with univocal Forms/monads.

⁸⁹ Although for a different reading that would accept an internal ‘composition’ within the henads, see T. Lankila (2010) 72.

9. Conclusion: Remaining Tensions

Given our solution proposed in Position (iv), there still remains an open question on the relation between the Limit/Unlimited and the One. One main issue is the opposition between the two principles: construed as henads, the Limit and Unlimited are both ‘one’ like the One-itself, yet how they acquire their distinct, opposed characters is not apparent. On the one hand Proclus construes the Unlimited as the power of the Limit, which suggests that the Unlimited is subordinated under the Limit, implying that the two principles are only *relatively* opposed. This would suggest that the Unlimited emerges from the Limit as its corresponding power, while it makes the One only responsible for deriving the Limit which mirrors the One’s character of unity. On the other hand, Proclus makes the Unlimited a separate principle from the Limit, and *PT* III.9 maintains that the One directly brings forth the Unlimited, alongside the Limit. If they come forth separately from the One, this suggests that the One pre-contains the opposed characters of the Limit and Unlimited. Proclus, however, would reject this suggestion: if the One has nothing of ‘all things’ in itself, *a posteriori* the One cannot pre-contain the opposed characters belonging to the Limit and Unlimited after it.⁹⁰

Proclus’ framework thus involves an unresolved *aporia*: the One functions as the ground, and thus principle, for the unity of the henads; however for Proclus, the One cannot imply any plurality found in Being—and thus also the incipient plurality found in both the henads and the Limit/Unlimited. One finds a lingering causal ‘gap’ in Proclus’ account of the Limit and Unlimited’s emergence from the One, which indicates a more general tension in Proclus’ system. It is this ‘gap’, in fact, which leads Proclus’ successor, Damascius, to alter the former’s framework radically and claim that the One, within itself, implies ‘traces’ of its opposites—i.e. the Limit/Unlimited.⁹¹

For our purposes, however, we can see that Proclus still maintains a coherent structure in understanding both the henads and the Limit and Unlimited as co-ordinated principles which together explain two distinct aspects in all beings: the kinds of different, unique characters found in the Forms and lower levels that originate in unity (with the henads), and the co-inherence of unity and plurality spread generically across all beings (with the Limit and Unlimited). This in turn informs the henads’ activity passed down and expressed throughout Being. In this respect Proclus successfully provides the scaffolding to understanding the causes of Being, which Damascius will help to refine greatly.⁹²

⁹⁰ See e.g. *In Parm.* 1107,29–1108,15.

⁹¹ Damascius, *De Principiis* I, 56,8–11 [Westerink-Combés]; cf. G. Van Riel (2002). I discuss this transition in more depth in a forthcoming monograph on the One’s causality in Proclus and Damascius.

⁹² Special thanks especially to Peter Adamson, Christoph Rapp, David Butorac, and Antonio Vargas for their insights and help in the preparation of this paper, originally part of my PhD dissertation, and also many thanks to two anonymous reviewers of an earlier draft of this piece.

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